

Female students' views on the reflections of school sports team life on their development: A phenomenological study

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Abstract. Sports is a new science that shapes human behavior and spiritual structure through individual or team games, movements, and various competitions, as well as improving individuals physically. In this study, it was aimed to examine the reflection of the reflection of school sports team life on their development. The research was a descriptive phenomenological study in qualitative design. A phenomenological study is a research that focuses on what people experience and how they experience what they experience. The population of the research consisted of female athlete students who study in public primary, secondary and high schools within the borders of Kepez District of Antalya province in the 2022-2023 academic year, and the sample of the study consisted of 8 female athlete students studying at primary and secondary school in Aslanlar Secondary School. As a data collection tool, a semi-structured interview form consisting of 5 questions prepared by the researcher and including questions about personal information was used. As a result of the research, it was found that sports team life had many positive benefits for social development, personality development, physical development and academic development.

Keywords: Sports, team life, development

Introduction

Education can generally be defined as the process of socializing the individual and raising an individual useful for the society. Thus, education is a process in which desired behavioral change occurs in the individual (Demirel, 2002). Education can be seen both as a behavior change and development process and as a process of adapting an individual to society. It can be said that the general purpose of education in today's modern societies is to help individuals adapt to the society where they live in a healthy way. In this respect, it can be thought that education both affects an individual's environment and develops him or her continuously. On the other hand, physical education has a very important place in the understanding of contemporary education. It can be thought that increasing the physical education lesson hours in basic education will be important in gaining the habit of doing regular sports. It can be expected that the person who does sports regularly will learn to respect his/her own body and personality first, and then to respect the society and other people living in the community.

12-14 age group is thought as the transition years from childhood to adulthood. The formation of personality and the establishment of character take place in these years. Children who make sports a habit are expected to live a happier and more meaningful life, to have more self-confidence, and to develop more physically and spiritually than children who do not do sports. The different opportunities offered to students make it easier for them to learn, and after a while their undesired behaviors start to change to desired ones. In the studies carried out in this area, it has been observed that the "The theory of multiple intelligences" based learning approach has a positive effect on the success of the students, develops

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positive behaviors towards the lesson, and decreases the disciplinary problems of the students who follow the rules (Korkmaz, 2001). Various activities carried out with children, physical education, cultural and sportive activities carried out with specific pedagogical responsibilities, and various competitions with the content of solidarity, together with planned physical activities that children will do, leave positive effects on their physical, social, mental and spiritual development, expanding their imaginations and giving them new opportunities and opens them new horizons (Muratlı, 2007).

In modern understanding, sport is seen as a very important mass education tool. Sports is a new branch of science that shapes human behavior and mental structure through individual or team games, movements, and various competitions, as well as improving individuals physically (Güven, 2006). Sports and physical training are the basis of a healthy life. For this reason, it is very important for children to be directed to sports at an early age and to make sports a habit. The role of the family is very important in making this habit a lifestyle in children. However, many families do not spare enough time for sports due to reasons such as workload, physical fatigue and not finding enough time, and it is a chore for their children to meet these needs. Parents' attention is very important in this regard, as children do not have knowledge about when and what sports they should do (Rohkohl, 2022; Orhan, 2019).

According to psychoanalyst theories, positive and negative experiences in the early period are considered to be very effective in character development. Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) wanted to emphasize how important the childhood period is by expressing that the experiences in childhood settle in the sub-conscious and are revealed as positive or negative symptoms in the 5 adult periods. Additionally, Erikson (1902-1994) stated that first of all, families, then social environment, friends and individuals of different age groups are influential in the development of children, and that various emotions, especially trust, which are gained at an early age, show themselves stronger in later ages and affect children positively. (Orhan & Ayan, 2018)

Sports, basically, are the integration of planned work, discipline, stability, goals and success. An individual who does sports is inevitably motivated to be organized and planned, to set goals and to achieve success. The child, who makes it a habit to be regular and systematic by doing sports, has goals. The same pattern is observed in the general life of a child, who is used to living in this way (Yalçın & Balcı, 2013). The first recommendation of field experts in school success is a regular sports training. The child, who releases his energy by acting and is included in a social group, is happier, his success with the support of his environment motivates him, his physical appearance, health, endurance and condition are noticed and respected by his friends and all these positive contributions affect the child's academic success in a positive way.

In this study, it is aimed to examine the reflections of school sports team life on female students' development. The problem statement and sub-problems of the research were expressed as follows:

Problem Statement

What are the opinions of female students on the reflections of school sports team life on their development?

Sub Problems:

1. What does school sports team life mean to female students?
2. What are the opinions of female students on the reflections of school sports team life on their social development?
3. What are the opinions of female students on the reflections of school sports team life on their personality development?
4. What are the opinions of female students on the reflections of school sports team life on their physical development?
5. What are the opinions of female students on the reflections of school sports team life on their academic development?

Method and paradigm of research

Knowledge constitute interest of this study is practical and the paradigm is interpretive as data were based on subjective and inter-subjective views and perspectives of the individuals (Gunbayi & Sorm, 2020). The research is a descriptive phenomenological study in qualitative design. A phenomenological study is research that focuses on what people experience and how they experience what they experience. The main goal of phenomenological study is to reveal what is in one's mind, that is, the essence of one's perception of lived experiences. (Creswell, 1998; Patton, 1990). In addition, phenomenological research focuses on the subjective experiences of the individual or individuals about a lived phenomenon, unlike case studies that investigate a phenomenon that is currently experienced in its context and unit. In phenomenological research, the focus is subjective experience rather than the phenomenon (Creswell, 1998; Patton, 1990, Polkinghorne, 1989)

Sampling

The population of the research consisted of female athletes who were educated in public primary, secondary and high schools within the boundaries of Antalya province Kepez District in the 2022-2023 academic year.

The sample, on the other hand, consisted of 8 athlete girls studying at primary and secondary school in Arslanlar Secondary School, which was selected on a voluntary basis with the purposeful sampling criterion sampling technique (Palys, 2008). Demographic characteristics of the athletes are given in the table below.

Table 1.

Distribution of demographic variables of the participants

Participant	Gender	Age	Duration to engage in sports
S1	Female	12	3 years
S2	Female	11	1 years
S3	Female	12	2 years
S4	Female	12	4 years
S5	Female	13	4 years
S6	Female	12	6 moths
S7	Female	10	4 years
S8	Female	12	1,5 years

Data collection

In the research, a semi-structured interview form consisting of 5 questions and questions about personal information prepared by the researcher, within the scope of the conceptual framework created by the review of the relevant literature was used. The interviews were recorded as audio files, and before the recording was started, the interviewee was informed and asked for her permission.

Ethical Procedures

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 17 decision numbered 354 on October 11th t, 2022, formal permission was obtained from the Antalya Provincial Directorate of National Education for the research numbered E-98057890-605.01-63864336 on November 21st 10th, 2022, an informed consent form was obtained from the participants before the interview and participants were informed that their names would not be mentioned and be given the alphabetical codes as S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7, S8.

Validity and Reliability of the Research

Validity and reliability of the qualitative data were carried out via the criteria of credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability (Lincoln and Guba, 1985): (1) for credibility, the researcher developed the semi-structured interview form via the review of relevant literature (2) for transferability a purposive sampling method was used to get opinions and experiences of participants based on their perspectives (3) for confirmability, Cohen's kappa coefficient of the themes of the transcripts created by two independent researchers was calculated as .83, a perfect level of agreement between themes d) for dependability all data collected were kept reachable to prove on demand (Landis and Koach, 1977; Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Cohen, Mannion and Morrison, 2007, Gunbayi, 2018).

Data Analysis

Verbatim transcripts were carried out by the researcher and recorded as audio files, and participants were delivered for their accuracy and confirmed by the participants. Qualitative text data regarding the sub-problems of the research were coded and thematic, descriptive and content analysis were done by using NVIVO software (Kelle, 1995; Cohen, Mannion & Morrison, 2007). In conclusion and discussion, the findings were interpreted and discussed with the relevant studies done in this field so far.

Findings

1. What sports team life means

The findings related to participants' opinions on the meaning of sports team life are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

What sports team life means

Themes	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
Unity							✓	✓
Being together							✓	✓
Solidarity						✓	✓	✓
Responsibility	✓					✓		
Healthy life and body		✓	✓		✓			
Pleasant time		✓		✓	✓			
Confidence	✓					✓		

As seen in Table 2, participants' opinions on what sports team life meant to them were gathered under 7 sub-themes and the themes of solidarity, healthy life and body and pleasant time were mentioned the most in themes. Some of participants' opinions on the meaning of sports team life are given below:

It means a high sense of responsibility. (S6)

It brings team spirit and makes you feel unity and togetherness. (S7)

It means unity and the ability to help each other. (S8)

Sports team life has a good place in my life because I enjoy it. (S2)

It contributes to a more self-confident individual in his social life. (S1)

When the answers given by the female students are interpreted; it was understood that sports team life meant to participants as unity, being together, solidarity, responsibility, healthy life and body, pleasant time, self-confidence.

2. Reflections of sports team life on social development

The findings related to participants' opinions on reflections of sports team life on social development are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

Reflections of sports team life on social development

Themes	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
making friends	✓	✓	✓	✓				
Ability to express one's self	✓							✓
Confidence		✓				✓	✓	
Being organized					✓			
Time management					✓			✓
being disciplined							✓	
Healthy lifestyle							✓	

As seen in Table 3, participants' opinions on reflections of sports team life on social development were gathered under 7 sub-themes and the theme of making friends were mentioned the most in themes. Some of participants' opinions on reflections of sports team life on social development are given below:

I gained the ability to make friends and express myself properly. (S1)

I gained social circle by making friends. (S3)

It allows me to be organized and use my time regularly. (S5)

Healthy living, discipline and self-confidence are the things that gave me the most. (S7)

When the answers given by the female students are interpreted, it was understood that reflections of sports team life on social development were making friends, ability to express one's self, confidence, being organized, time management, being disciplined and healthy lifestyle.

3. Reflections of sports team life on personality development

The findings related to participants' opinions on reflections of sports team life on personality development are presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

Reflections of sports team life on personality development

Themes	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
Discipline habit	✓							
Ability to be organized	✓				✓			
Increasing self-confidence		✓						
Doing activities			✓					
Living in unity				✓	✓			
Earning respect						✓		
Happiness						✓		
Empathy							✓	
Communication							✓	
Gaining strength								✓

As seen in Table 4, participants’ opinions on reflections of sports team life on personal development were gathered under 10 sub-themes and the themes of ability to be organized and living in unity were mentioned the most in themes. Some of participants’ opinions on reflections of sports team life on personal development are given below:

There is definitely. Since sports ethics and discipline are reflected in daily life, it gives us the ability to be disciplined and organized in the rest of our lives. (S1)

Sports life has been very beneficial for my personality development. It has been an activity in my life. (S3)

I learned to live in unity and togetherness. (S4)

It allows me to be organized as it is a collective team work. (S5)

Since the day I started my sports life, I learned to think for the other person. (S7)

When the answers given by the female students are interpreted, it was understood that reflections of sports team life on personal development were discipline habit, ability to be organized, increasing self-confidence, doing activities, living in unity, earning respect, happiness, empathy, communication and gaining strength.

4. Reflections of sports team life on physical development

The findings related to participants’ opinions on reflections of sports team life on physical development are presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

Reflections of sports team life on physical development

Themes	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
Being strong	✓		✓				✓	
Being agile	✓		✓					
Balance	✓							
Muscle coordination development	✓						✓	
Bone development	✓							
Height growth		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Athletic body				✓				
Healthy body	✓		✓					

As seen in Table 4, participants’ opinions on reflections of sports team life on physical development were gathered under 8 sub-themes and the themes of height growth was the most mentioned in themes. Some of participants’ opinions on reflections of sports team life on personal development are given below:

I've grown too tall. (S2)

I gained muscle development and a strong body. (S7)

You have an athletic body. (S4)

It made me stronger, agile and healthy. (S1)

When the answers given by the female students are interpreted; it was understood that reflections of sports team life on physical development were being strong, being agile, balance, muscle coordination development, bone development, height growth, athletic body and healthy body.

5. Reflections of sports team life on academic development

The findings related to participants' opinions on reflections of sports team life on academic development are presented in Table 6.

Table 6.

Reflections of sports team life on academic development

Themes	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
Having priority	✓							
Appreciation		✓						
Being protectable								
Dreaming about the future				✓	✓	✓	✓	
Being practical and quick	✓							✓
Attention and focus skill			✓					
Strong memory		✓						

As seen in Table 4, participants' opinions on reflections of sports team life on academic development were gathered under 7 sub-themes and the theme of dreaming about the future was the most mentioned in themes. Some of participants' opinions on reflections of sports team life on personal development are given below:

It has been my priority in sports activities in school. (S1)

I am appreciated in school for being disciplined. /S2)

I can imagine being a famous athlete. (S4)

I think I will improve my sport and go to international matches. (S7)

When the answers given by the female students are interpreted, it was understood that reflections of sports team life on academic development were having priority, appreciation, being protectable, dreaming about the future, being practical and quick, attention and focus skill and strong memory.

Discussion and conclusion

When the research findings were examined, it was seen that sports team life meant unity, healthy life and enjoyable time for students. The students stated that by doing sports, they gained the awareness of helping themselves and their environment. In this way, they also stated that the concept of unity had a very important place in their sports life. This finding was consistent with the findings of Kulaber's (2021) study called "Examination of sportsmanship orientation of students studying at sports high school and physical education and sports school in terms of some variables", in which it was found that the sportsmanship orientation of the participants who did active sports had more sportsmanship orientation than those who did not do active sport.

When the findings related to the second sub-problem were examined, it was seen that the reflections of sports team life on social development were making friends, ability to express one's self, confidence, being organized, time management, being disciplined and healthy lifestyle. When participants' expressions considered, it was understood that the most contribution of sports team life was to make

friends. Additionally, it was seen that students thought that they prioritized making friends through their sports team experiences and that they also acquired various personal development skills.

When the reflections of sports team life on personality development were examined, it was seen that the biggest gain of the students was to acquire the habit of discipline, as well as gain order skills and increase their self-confidence. In addition, it was seen that doing activities, living in unity, earning respect, happiness, empathy and communication skills also increased. When participants' expressions considered, it was understood that they thought that the greatest contribution was the ability to live in unity and organized. This finding was consistent with the result of Taştan's (2020) study called "Examination of life satisfaction and sports participation motives of athletes interested in some racquet sports (the example of Kayseri province)", in which a significant relationship was found between the life satisfaction of the volunteers who were studying at secondary and high school levels and their motivation to participate in racquet sports.

When the reflections of sports team life on physical development were examined, it was seen that there were reflections such as being strong, being agile, balance, muscle coordination development, bone development, height growth, athletic body and healthy body. Among these reflections, it was found that the most contribution was on height growth. This finding was consistent with the result of the research by Yaran M. (2014) called "Investigation of sleep quality and quality of life in university students who make sports and who do not" and in this study the sleep quality and quality of life of the students of the university students, who did active sports and did not do active sports, were examined. It was found that there was no significant difference between the sleep qualities of university students who did sports compared to those who did not, but their quality of life was higher.

When the reflections of sports team life on academic development were examined, it was seen that the reflections were skills such as having priority, appreciation, being protectable, dreaming about the future, being practical and quick, attention and focus skill and strong memory. Among them, it was found that dreaming about the future was the most common. These findings were supported by the view of Bradley, Keane and Crawford (2013) that promoting participation in school sport and providing access to a range of team and individual sports throughout the secondary school years may be a beneficial way to improve students' school attainment.

Recommendations

In line with the findings, following suggestions were put forward:

The study group of the research was limited to 8 athlete girls in a secondary school in Antalya Kepez District. By conducting the research with more secondary school students, more female athletes can be reached.

The study group of the research was limited to secondary school students. The research can also be conducted with students in other education and training categories.

Looking at the results of the research, it is seen that school sports experience causes positive developments in students mentally, socially, personally and academically. From this point of view, it can be suggested that teachers should direct students to more sports activities and thus cause positive developments, including the transformation of negative behavioral characteristics.

According to the results of the research, it was seen that the students attach great importance to issues such as making friends, being self-confident, being respected, and the development of feelings of unity. It has been observed that they think that they have improved in these subjects thanks to their sports life. For this reason, it can be suggested to parents and teachers to encourage students to be directed towards sports life and sports teams.

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Ethical approval

In the writing process of the study titled “**Female students’ views on the reflection of school sports team life on their development: A phenomenological study**”, the rules of scientific, ethical and citation were followed; it was undertaken by the authors of this study that no falsification was made on the collected data. “Journal Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research [JAQMER] and Editor” had no responsibility for all ethical violations to be encountered, and all responsibility belongs to the authors and that the study was not submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing environment.

Ethics committee approval

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 17 decision numbered 354 on October 11th, 2022.